

Project Title	Expanding FAIR solutions across EOSC
Project Acronym	FAIR-IMPACT
Grant Agreement No.	101057344
Start Date of Project	2022-06-01
Duration of Project	36 months
Project Website	https://fair-impact.eu

1 M2.9 FAIR implementation action plans ready (gamma)

Work Package	WP2
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Due Date	2025-04-30
Date of report	2025-04-30
Version	V1.0
DOI	10.5281/zenodo.15311010

Dissemination Level

<input checked="" type="checkbox"/>	PU: Public
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<input type="checkbox"/>	RE: Restricted to a group specified by the consortium (including the Commission)
<input type="checkbox"/>	CO: Confidential, only for members of the consortium (including the Commission)

2 Versioning and contribution history

Version	Date	Author	Notes
0.1	23.04.2025	Joy Davidson (DCC-UEDIN)	TOC and V0.1
0.2	30.04.2025	Vasso Kalaitzi (KNAW-DANS)	review of v0.1 and additions
1.0	30.04.2025	Joy Davidson (DCC-UEDIN)	updated version for internal use

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FAIR-IMPACT has received funding from the European Commission's Horizon Europe funding programme for research and innovation programme under the Grant Agreement no. 101057344. The content of this document does not represent the opinion of the European Commission, and the European Commission is not responsible for any use that might be made of such content.

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TERMINOLOGY

Terminology/Acronym	Description
FIF	FAIR Implementation Framework
FAIR Implementation Action Plan	Defining a set of objectives, identifying relevant actors and timeframes for progress FAIR implementation
FAIR Implementation Story	FAIRsFAIR developed the concept of the FAIR Implementation story to illustrate good practices in research communities and organisations to support the implementation of the FAIR principles. This practice is continued in the follow-up project FAIR-IMPACT.
RPO	Research Performing Organisation

1. Introduction

The FAIR-IMPACT project is a 3-year EU Funded project aiming to provide coordination and support mechanisms for the implementation of FAIR-enabling practices, tools and services across disciplines at national, European and institutional level. One of the main mechanism was an elaborate set of support programmes across these three years, providing a) expert (in-kind) non-financial support,¹ b) financial support through cascading grants,² and c) open FAIR Implementation Workshops.³ Through these programmes, the project managed to provide support to a wide range of stakeholders. During the journey of FAIR implementation through expert support, the supported stakeholders were assisted in creating their own FAIR implementation action plans. Although these plans were very helpful for the support programme participants, the teams involved argued that the wider public would profit more through the recording of these experiences in the form of FAIR Adoption and Implementation Stories. A dedicated page⁴ exists on the FAIR-IMPACT project listing these Stories, providing insight on the process, challenges, best practices, experience and results on behalf of the supported participants. The stories are also available on the FAIR-IMPACT Zenodo community.⁵ To share experiences in developing and implementing their plans more widely, peer exchange workshops were a key feature included in each of the expert, non-financial in-kind support programmes.

2. Description of the Milestone

2.1 Role of the Milestone

This milestone report describes the process that involved the creation of FAIR Implementation action plans during the expert, non-financial support programmes.

2.2 Verification Means

FAIR-IMPACT's open calls to join our series of expert, non-financial, support programmes were targeted to those who are just getting started with supporting the FAIR Principles or are less advanced on their FAIR-enabling journey. Successful applicants worked with FAIR-IMPACT mentors over a period of nine months to learn how to support the uptake of FAIR-enabling practices. This included participation in a series of 6-10 virtual workshops, carrying out homework assignments, and receiving one-to-one support. The detailed programme per round is available on the FAIR-IMPACT website.

¹ <https://fair-impact.eu/apply-non-financial-support>

² <https://fair-impact.eu/apply-financial-support>

³ <https://fair-impact.eu/events/fair-implementation-workshops>

⁴ <https://fair-impact.eu/implementation-adoption-stories>

⁵ <https://zenodo.org/communities/fair-impact/records?q=&l=list&p=1&s=10&sort=newest>

Between January 2024 and March 2025, FAIR-IMPACT delivered support for three key stakeholder communities: Research Performing Organisations (RPOs), Repositories and Data Service Providers, and National Level Initiatives.

Support Programme	Dates of delivery	Number of participating teams
Research Performing Organisations (RPO) programme ⁶	February 2024-October 2024	20
First running of the Repositories and Data Service Providers programme ⁷	January 2024 -September 2024	6
First running of the National Level Initiatives programme ⁸	February 2024-October 2024	4
Second running of the Repositories and Data Service Providers programme ⁹	September 2024-March 2025	9
Second running of the National Level Initiatives programme ¹⁰	September 2024-January 2025	37

Figure 1. Expert, non-financial support programme infoThe lists of successful applicants for each of the support programmes in the table are provided on the relevant web pages of the FAIR-IMPACT website.

During the expert support programmes, the mentors assisted the successful participants in creating their own FAIR implementation action plans. These plans exist as internal documents, as they contain more information than what is needed to provide examples for the public. In place of the plans, this journey of FAIR implementation is made available on Zenodo and the FAIR-IMPACT website with a web page dedicated to FAIR Adoption and Implementation Stories. These stories provide insight on the process, experiences of successful applicants, the challenges they needed to address together with their mentors, best practices, results and guidance.

⁶ <https://fair-impact.eu/2nd-open-call-support-opens-30-august>

⁷ ibid

⁸ ibid

⁹ <https://fair-impact.eu/2nd-open-call-route-1-expert-non-financial-support-open>

¹⁰ <https://fair-impact.eu/second-call-national-level-initiatives>

3. Approach Taken

During each of the support programmes, participants received dedicated support to carry out the steps in the FAIR Implementation Framework (FIF)¹¹ (Figure 1) which was designed to help our stakeholders to consider their drivers, self-assess their current FAIR-enabling capacity and to help them develop FAIR implementation action and engagement plans.

Figure 2. FAIR Implementation Framework

To support the development of action plans, participants were provided with templates and workbooks to be completed iteratively over the course of the support programmes with support from their FAIR-IMPACT mentors.

For the Research Performing Organisations (RPOs) support programme, each participating team was provided with a workbook to enable them to work through the FIF stages. The workbook focuses on four thematic areas: developing or refining data policies to be more FAIR-enabling, developing support services for data management planning, trustworthy data curation, and building skills for producing and using FAIR data. The ACME-FAIR rubrics¹² which were developed in the FAIRsFAIR project were adapted for each of the thematic areas in the workbook.

¹¹ <https://fair-impact.eu/fair-implementation-framework>

¹² <https://www.fairsfair.eu/acme-fair-guide-rpo>

To support participants in the Repositories and Data Services support programme, a number of instruments were created to help the teams work through the FIF stages: two worksheets helped participants identify their drivers and to self-assess their current and desired capabilities in different relevant areas. These two instruments then led participants to the development of their FAIR implementation action plan, which they could develop in a provided template instrument. This plan was later enriched with a template for Stakeholder Engagement strategies, which participants included after participating in the related workshop.

For the National Level Initiatives support programme, a preparatory questionnaire and self-assessment checklist was shared with participants prior to the start of the programme to help them reflect on their main drivers, policies, and challenges for implementing the FAIR principles. The questionnaire and templates for analysing responses are available for reuse.¹³

The action plans that have been developed are intended to be used as internal planning tools by the participating teams and were shared only with the FAIR-IMPACT mentors. To share experiences in developing and implementing their plans more widely, peer exchange workshops were a key feature included in each of the expert, non-financial support programmes. The participants have also developed FAIR Implementation Stories¹⁴ which provide an overview of the aims and actions taken in relation to their action plans. These are made publicly accessible via our Zenodo community and website.

There is an associated KPI for this activity in relation to the number of plans produced (low=15, medium=25, high=40). As of 30 April 2025, we have reached 'high' KPI.

¹³ FAIR-IMPACT T2.5 Preparatory questionnaire and self-assessment checklist for national-level initiatives <https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.14883638>

¹⁴ FAIR Implementation Stories <https://fair-impact.eu/implementation-adoption-stories>